

Volatile terpenoid composition and antimicrobial activity of flowers of *Melia azedarach* Linn. from north west Himalayas, India

G. C. Kharkwal^a, C. Pande^{*a}, G. Tewari^a, A. Panwar^b and V. Pande^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Kumaun University, Nainital-263 002, Uttarakhand, India

E-mail : pandechitra@yahoo.in

^bDepartment of Biotechnology, Bhimtal Campus, Kumaun University, Nainital, Uttarakhand, India

Manuscript received online 29 May 2014, revised 14 June 2014, accepted 07 August 2014

Abstract : Essential oil of *Melia azedarach* Linn. obtained by hydro distillation using Clevenger apparatus was analyzed by gas chromatography (GC) and gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). Eighteen compounds were identified representing 92.21% of the total oil. The oil contains the highest proportion of oxygenated sesquiterpene hydrocarbons (73.99%). (*E*)-Nerolidol (70%), *n*-nonanal (4.78%), (*Z*)-nerolidol (3.99%) are the predominant compounds along with cumarene (1.34%), *n*-decanal (1.31%), as minor constituents. *In vitro* antimicrobial activity of oil was conducted against microbial strains including one Gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*) and five Gram-negative (*Proteus vulgaris*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella enterica*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*) bacteria as well as two fungi (*Pichia guilliermondii*, *Candida albicans*) using agar well diffusion method.

Keywords : *Melia azedarach*, Meliaceae, essential oil, (*E*)-nerolidol, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Meliaceae, a versatile family of great importance in bio-organic research, comprising 50 genera and 550 species, is distributed in tropical and subtropical regions of the world. In India, the family is represented by 17 genera and 72 species¹. It is wide spread and naturalized in most of the tropics and subtropical countries growing at an elevation of up to 1800 m in the Himalayas². Different preparations of various parts of *M. azedarach* are being used for controlling several diseases^{3,4}. The powder of the dried fruits of this plant is claimed to be an effective therapy for the treatment of diabetes⁵. Leaves of *M. azedarach* are used for anaemia, measles, jaundice, wounds, pimples and bloody piles⁶. The pulp of the fruit is a favourite remedy for colic and is said to relieve pain most effectively among the labouring classes and also acts as an anthelmintic⁷. Various ethnomedicinal applications of *M. azedarach* have also been reported in the treatment of skin diseases such as eczema, ulcerative wounds, syphilitic ulcers, leprosy etc.^{7,8}. The essential oil composition of leaves of *M. dubia* have been reported from Eastern Ghats of Peninsular, India and the essential oil composition of fruit and flowers of *M. azedarach* have

also been reported from Iran^{9,10}. To the best of our knowledge, there have been no attempts to study the essential oil composition and antimicrobial properties of *M. azedarach* from Uttarakhand.

Results and discussion

The flowers of *M. azedarach* on steam distillation gave pale yellow coloured essential oil (Yield : 0.09%). The compounds were identified on the basis of correlation of their mass spectra and comparison with those given in the literature. GC and GC/MS analysis of essential oil of flowers collected from Jeolikot, Nainital (Uttarakhand) showed the presence of 27 compounds, of which 18 compounds were identified, representing 92.21% of the total oil. Earlier reports showed that the leaf essential oil consisted chiefly of monoterpene hydrocarbons (35.71%) and oxygenated monoterpenes (27.98%), accompanied by relatively smaller amount of alkanes (11.17%), sesquiterpene hydrocarbons (9.26%) and phenylpropanoid (3.90%), camphene (21.68%) being the major component⁹. Our study showed the presence of *trans*-nerolidol (70.00%), *cis*-nerolidol (3.99%), *n*-nonanal (4.78%) and cumarene (1.34%) as major constituents (Fig. 1) in flower essential

Fig. 1. Gas chromatogram of the essential oil of *M. azedarach* Linn.

oil (Table 1). Essential oil of flowers from Iran contained *trans*-nerolidol (38.9%), viridiflorol (8.1%), bicyclo-germacerene (8.2%), β -caryophyllene (7.2%), *cis*-caryophyllene (7.1%), 1,8-cineole (6.1%) and camphor (5.7%) as major constituents while the fruit oil of this plant contained aromadendrene (21.9%), bicyclo-germacerene (13.7%), globulol (8.1%), germacerene D (5.6%) and allo-aromadendrene (4.7%) as major constituents¹⁰. Camphor, 1,8-cineole, viridiflorol, globulol and germacerene D were totally absent in our report.

The oil of *M. azedarach* flower was tested for antimicrobial activity against six standard strains of bacteria and two standard fungal strains. The results of *in vitro* test showed that the oil had moderate activity against all the examined pathogens on the basis of zone of inhibition and MIC values. The essential oil of the plant showed mean zone of inhibition for the bacterial strains which varied from 12.33 ± 0.58 (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) to 9.67 ± 0.58 (*Escherichia coli*) with the MIC values ranging from 150 $\mu\text{L/ml}$ to 175 $\mu\text{L/ml}$. The oil exhibited

Table 1. Volatile terpenoid composition of flowering aerial parts of the *M. azedarach* Linn.

Sr. no.	Compds. ^a	RI _{exp} ^b	RI ^c	Percentage (%)
1.	<i>n</i> -Nonanal	1105	1100	4.78
2.	<i>n</i> -Decanal	1199	1201	1.31
3.	Isocaryophyllene	1398	1408	0.97
4.	β-Caryophyllene	1422	1417	0.41
5.	Unknown	1452	–	1.50
6.	α-Acordiene	1465	1464	0.37
7.	Cumarene	1468	1470	1.34
8.	Bicyclogermacrene	1500	1500	0.59
9.	<i>cis</i> -Nerolidol	1527	1531	3.99
10.	<i>trans</i> -Nerolidol	1565	1561	70.0
11.	Octadecane	1790	1800	0.76
12.	Phytone	1836	–	0.86
13.	Ethyl hexadecanoate	1986	1992	0.82
14.	<i>n</i> -Eicosane	1989	2000	0.52
15.	<i>n</i> -Heneicosane	2089	2100	1.19
16.	<i>n</i> -Docosane	2188	2200	0.96
17.	<i>n</i> -Tricosane	2286	2300	1.70
18.	<i>n</i> -Pentacosane	2488	2500	1.20
19.	<i>n</i> -Nonacosane	2879	2900	0.44
	Total			93.71
	Oxygenated monoterpene			6.09
	Sesquiterpene hydrocarbon			3.68
	Oxygenated sesquiterpene			73.99
	Others			9.95
	Total			93.71

^aMode of identification : Retention index, on Equity-5 column, MS (GC-MS). ^bRetention indice determined on the Equity-5 column using an *n*-alkane homologous series (C₉–C₃₃); ^cRetention indices from the literature (Adams, 2007), t = trace (< 0.01%), bold numbers indicate major constituents, t = trace (< 0.10%).

maximum activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* with inhibition zone of 12.33 ± 0.58 mm diameter and MIC 150 µL/ml followed by *Klebsiella pneumonia* (ZI; 11.67 ± 0.58 mm, MIC; 175 µL/ml), *Staphylococcus aureus* (ZI; 10.67 ± 0.58 mm, MIC; 150 µL/ml), *Salmonella enteric* (ZI; 10.67 ± 0.58 mm, MIC; 150 µL/ml), *Proteus vulgaris* (ZI; 10.0 ± 0 mm, MIC; 150 µL/ml) and *Escherichia coli* (ZI; 9.67 ± 0.58 mm, MIC; 175 µL/ml).

The oil showed good activity against only *Pichia guilliermondii* standard pathogenic fungi (MIC; 200 µL/ml). No activity was observed to be shown by this plant against *Candida albicans*. To the best of our knowledge, no work is reported in literature so far on the essential oil composition and antimicrobial activity of flower of this species from Uttarakhand region.

Experimental

Plant collection and identification :

M. azedarach was collected in May 2011 from Jeolikot, Nainital (Uttarakhand, India). The plant was identified by Professor Y. P. S. Pangtey, Botany Department, Kumaun University, Nainital, which has been deposited in the herbarium repository of Botanical Survey of India, Dehradun for future reference (Acc. No. 113659).

Isolation of essential oil :

Fresh aerial parts (2 kg) were subjected to hydro distillation using Clevenger apparatus for 3 h. The essential oil was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate (Merck) until the last traces of water were removed and then stored in a dark glass bottle at 4 °C prior to GC and GC-MS

Table 2. Antimicrobial activity of essential oil of *Melia azedarach* Linn.

Sr. no.	Microorganism	MTCC	Standard antibiotics					
			<i>Melia azedarach</i>		Gentamicin		Kanamycin	
	Bacteria		ZI ^a (mm)	MIC ^b (µL/ml)	ZI ^a (mm)	MIC (µL/ml)	ZI ^a (mm)	MIC ^b (µL/ml)
1.	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	3384	11.67 ± 0.21	175	10.67 ± 0.05	50	10.67 ± 0.08	50
2.	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	3103	10.67 ± 0.13	150	17.33 ± 0.15	50	16.33 ± 0.25	50
3.	<i>Salmonella enteric</i>	3224	10.67 ± 0.07	175	14.67 ± 0.05	50	13.33 ± 0.09	75
4.	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	443	9.67 ± 0.04	175	10.67 ± 0.03	50	9.67 ± 0.05	100
5.	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	424	12.33 ± 0.11	150	13.33 ± 0.24	50	12.67 ± 0.07	50
6.	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	1771	10.00 ± 0.00	150	15.67 ± 0.09	50	13.33 ± 0.06	75
	Fungus				ZI ^a (mm)		Standard Nystatin (µL/ml)	
7.	<i>Pichia guilliermondii</i>	4052	7.67±0.07	200	15±0.13		250	
8.	<i>Candida albicans</i>	227	ND	ND	13±0.31		250	

^aInhibition zone diameter (mm), size of well 3 mm not included in ZI; ^bMinimum inhibitory concentration values in 1000 µL/ml to 5 µL/ml; ND = Not detected.

analysis. The yield of the essential oil obtained from flower of *M. azedarach* was 0.09% (v/w).

Analysis of essential oil :

The oil was analysed by using a Shimadzu 2010 auto system GC fitted with Rtx-5 column and FID detector. The column temperature was programmed at 80 °C (hold time 2 min) to 210 °C (hold time 5 min) at 3 °C min⁻¹ and then 210–300 °C at 20 °C min⁻¹ with final hold time of 15 min, using N₂ at 30.0 mL/min column head pressure as carrier gas, the injector temperature was 270 °C and detector (FID, Flame ionisation detector) temperature 280 °C. The GC-MS used was Autosystem 2010 GC (Rtx-5, 30 m × 0.25 mm, i.d. film thickness 0.25 µm) coupled with Shimadzu QP 2010 plus with thermal desorption system TD 20 with (Rtx-5) fused silica capillary column (30 m × 0.25 mm with film thickness 0.25 µm). The column temperature was 80 °C (hold time for 2 min) to 210 °C (hold time 5 min) at 3 °C min⁻¹ and then 210–300 °C at 20 °C min⁻¹ with final hold time of 21 min, using helium as carrier gas. The injector temperature was 230 °C and 0.2 µL in *n*-hexane, with split ratio of 1 : 30 MS were taken at 70 eV with a mass range of 40–650 amu.

Identification of the components :

Identification of constituents was done by on the basis of Retention Index, MS Library search (NIST and Wiley) and also by comparing with the MS literature data¹¹.

Antimicrobial activity :

The essential oil was screened for antimicrobial activity against bacteria *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (MTCC3384), *Staphylococcus aureus* (MTCC3103), *Salmonella enterica* (MTCC3224), *Escherichia coli* (MTCC443), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (MTCC424), *Proteus vulgaris* (MTCC1771) and fungus *Pichia guilliermondii* (MTCC 4052) and *Candida albicans* (MTCC227) were prepared by emulsifying single colony in 5 ml of sterilized required nutrient broth. Tubes with required nutrient broth and inoculated bacterial cultures were incubated overnight at 37 °C for 24 h. Turbid cultures were then used as stock inoculums. The bacterial strains were obtained from the Institute of Microbial Technology (IMTECH), Chandigarh, India, as Microbial Type Culture Collection (MTCC). All bacterial strains were cultured and main-

tained in Microbiology Laboratory, Department of Biotechnology, Bhimtal campus, Kumaun University, Nainital by regular sub culturing and preserved as glycerol stock at –20 °C for further use.

Zone of inhibition (ZI) and minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) :

Antimicrobial activities of the essential oil against above microorganism and a few reference materials were determined by Agar Well Diffusion method^{12,13}. The organisms were cultured in nutrient broth (bacterial strains) and malt yeast broth (fungal strains) and the tests were carried out on Mueller Hinton agar and Potato Dextrose agar plates respectively. The inoculums of the microbial strains were prepared from 24 h broth cultures, the cultures were adjusted to 10⁶ CFU/ml with sterile water. The different concentration range from 5 µL/ml to 1000 µL/ml of essential oils was prepared by dissolving them in hexane. Muller Hinton agar and Potato Dextrose agar were poured into petridishes. After solidification, 100 µL of test strains were spread on the media plates separately. Care was taken to ensure proper homogenization.

The experiment was performed under strict aseptic conditions. After the inoculation, a well was made in the plates with sterile borer (3 mm). The oil samples (30 µL/well) of different concentrations (5 µL/ml to 1000 µL/ml) were introduced into the well and plates were incubated at 37 °C for 24 h. All samples were tested in triplicate. Microbial growth was determined by measuring the zone of inhibition. Gentamicin and Kanamycin for bacterial strain and Nystatin for fungal strain were used as positive control. Hexane was used as negative control. The MIC value was defined as the lowest concentration of the volatile oil required for inhibiting the growth of each microorganism.

Conclusion

The oil of *M. azedarach* was observed to be a rich source of *trans*-nerolidol. *Trans*-nerolidol is used as a flavoring agent in perfumery. It is also currently under testing as a skin penetration enhancer for the transdermal delivery of therapeutic drugs¹⁴. Our results suggest promising antimicrobial properties of *M. azedarach*, which may be useful for pharmaceutical treatment and natural therapies.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to the Head, Department of Chemistry, Kumaun University, Nainital, for providing the necessary instrumentation and laboratory facilities, MOEF, New Delhi for financial assistance and also to AIRF, JNU, New Delhi, for providing GC and GC-MS facility.

References

1. M. Ahmedulla and M. P. Nayar, "Endemic plants of the Indian region", BSI, Calcutta, 1986.
2. M. R. Khan, M. Kihara and A. D. Omoloso, *Fitoterapia*, 2001, **72**, 575.
3. G. M. Watt and B. Brandwijk, "The medicinal and poisonous plants of Southern and Eastern Africa", E. S. Livingstone Ltd., Edinburgh, London, 1962, p. 745.
4. S. R. Baquar, "Medicinal and poisonous plants of Pakistan", Printas, Karachi, Pakistan, 1989, p. 279.
5. M. Ahmad, R. Qureshi, M. Arshad, M. A. Khan and M. Zafer, *Pak. J. Botany*, 2009, **41**, 2777.
6. S. Z. Husain, R. N. Malik, M. Javaid and S. Bibi, *Pak. J. Botany*, 2008, **40**, 1897.
7. W. D. Dymock, C. J. H. Warden and D. Hooper, "Pharmacographia Indica", Jayyed Press, New Delhi, 1890.
8. G. Watt, "Dictionary of the economic products of India", Office of the Superintendent, Government of India, Calcutta, 1893, p. 221.
9. M. A. H. Nagalakshmi, D. Thangadurai, T. Anuradha and T. Pullaiah, *Flavour. Frag. J.*, 2001, **16**, 241.
10. J. S. Ghomi, T. Ahmadi and H. Batooli, *Chem. Nat. Comp.*, 2010, **46**, 816.
11. R. P. Adams, "Identification of essential oil components by Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry", Carol Stream, IL, Allured Publishing Corp., 2007.
12. C. F. Bagamboula and M. Uyttendaele, *J. Food Microbiol.*, 2004, **21**, 33.
13. C. Perez, M. Pauli and P. Bazerque, *Acta Biol. Med. Exper.*, 1990, **15**, 113.
14. K. Moser, *European J. Pharmaceutics and Biopharmaceutics*, 2001, **52**, 103.

